

WAYS TO USE MODERN METHODS OF EMPLOYMENT OF LABOR RESOURCES IN THE REGION

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Abstract

In this article, the labor resources in the region, their structure, the assessment and analysis of the employment of the population in the conditions of the digital economy, the process of studying the characteristics of the employment of labor resources and the factors affecting it, and the new, modern ways of employment are evaluated.

Key words

employment, labor resources, employment status, ability to work, balance of labor resources, labor sector, labor market, freelancing, outsourcing, outsourcing.

The main goal of all the reforms implemented in Uzbekistan is human well-being and ensuring a decent standard of living. This, in turn, depends on factors such as the state's creation of all conditions for effective employment of the population, including a favorable business environment for entrepreneurs, investment, tax policy, transparency, justice of the judicial system. Because 90% of the jobs created in our country are contributed by the private sector, and the development of the economy is related to the development of small and medium-sized businesses.

The tension of the demographic situation in Uzbekistan, the rapid growth of the population and the entry of more than 500 000 young people into the labor market every year make the issue of stable employment of the population very urgent.

Labor resources in Uzbekistan as of January 1, 2021 are 19,1 million people, the economically active population is 14,8 million people, total employment 13,2 million. people, of which 5,7 million are in the official sector of the economy people (43,3%), 5,6 million in the informal sector of the economy people (42,8%), 1,6 million people in need of employment. people (10,5%) and those who went to work abroad – 1,8 million organized a person.

In the past 5 years, digitization of most processes in the labor sector, adaptation of labor statistics to the standards of the International Labor Organization, provision of its real indicators, development and wide use of new forms of employment, transparency and convenient and fast implementation of all services to the population through electronic platforms have been achieved.

The new version of the Law "On Employment of the Population" was adopted in 2022 and it became the Law with direct effect. It reflects the main principles of the state in the field of employment and is based on modern labor law norms. In particular, new means of regulating the labor market, in particular, promotion of entrepreneurship, self-employment, vocational training of the unemployed, improvement of skills, consideration of length of service, payment of unemployment benefits, employment agencies, citizens performing temporary work outside the republic, and other important areas were covered.

In the conditions of the digital economy, the system-content method is widely used to study the employment structure of the population. This method involves the analysis of the studied object within a larger object. For example, when researching labor resources using the system-content method, although the object - labor resources is considered, it is necessary to study a larger object - the population and its quantitative and qualitative changes, as well as its location characteristics and factors affecting it.

The analysis of the employment situation in the Bukhara region allows to reveal the unique features of the region. In the context of structural changes in the economy, it is important to study social demographic factors and their characteristics when studying the employment situation in Bukhara region.

As of January 1, 2023, the total population of Bukhara region is 2016,9 thousand people organized.⁸⁹ According to the data of the current year, the share of urban residents in the total population was 36,7% (715,5 thousand people) and rural population - 63,3% (1231,4 thousand people). Among the working-age population, older people predominate in urban areas, while younger people make up the majority in rural areas. In the emergence of such a situation, the main part of people with certain labor qualifications, high education and life experience strive to find work in the city in accordance with the quality indicators of their labor force, in which the influence of factors such as good working conditions in urban areas, relatively high wages, timely payment of wages is significant. In general, in terms of the length of the average age of the population in the region, the city is ahead,

⁸⁹ <https://stat.uz/en/press-center/news-of-committee/39087-buxoro-viloyati-doimiy-aholisi-sonining-taqsimlanishi-3#:~:text=As%20of%20April%201%2C%202023,the%20corresponding%20period%20of%202022.>

and this situation is partly explained by the high level of medical services provided in urban areas. Despite the influence of these factors, the number of people living in rural areas compared to the city has been increasing year by year.

As of April 1, 2023, the total resident population of the Bukhara region amounted to 2016,6 thousand people, an increase of 1,7% compared to with the corresponding period of 2022.

Of them:

The number of women – 1005,8 thousand people,

The number of men – 1010,8 thousand people,

In urban areas – 743,3 thousand people,

In rural areas – 1273,3 thousand people.⁹⁰

According to statistics, over the past three years, the population of the region has increased by 3,4% or 69,7 thousand people.

During this period, the rural population increased by 10,3% or 141,9 thousand people, the urban population - by 3,7% or 27,8 thousand people. Thus, the rural population increased by 114,1 thousand people more than the urban population.

1-table

Dynamics of population change in Bukhara region (thousands of people)

Indicators	years			Change in 2023 compared to 2021	
	2023	2022	2021	+,-	%
Total population	2016,6	1923,9	1946,9	+69,7	103,4
From this: Townsppeople	743,3	709,5	715,5	+27,8	103,7
Villagers	1373,3	1214,4	1231,4	+141,9	110,3

This situation can be explained, on the one hand, by the high rates of natural growth in rural areas, and on the other hand, the creation of conditions for the rural population to run their own households had an effect to a certain extent. Now let's see how such factors affected the level of employment in the region.

In general, the Bukhara region is poorly provided with labor resources. At the beginning of 2023, the population density in the Bukhara region will be 1 sq. km. was 42,3 people per km, or 1,5 times less than in Uzbekistan.

⁹⁰ <https://stat.uz/en/press-center/news-of-committee/39087-buxoro-viloyati-doimiy-aholisi-sonining-taqsimlanishi-3#:~:text=As%20of%20April%201%2C%202023,the%20corresponding%20period%20of%202022.>

However, although the Bukhara region as a whole is poorly provided with labor resources, it has areas with different population densities. For this reason, three regions can be distinguished in the Bukhara region: regions with low labor resources (Jondor, Olot, Peshku, Karakol and Karovulbazar regions), with labor resources (Shofirkon region) and regions with an excess of labor resources (Bukhara region, Kogon region, Kogon, Vobkent, Romitan, Gijduvan and Bukhara regions).

In 2021-2023, we grouped the districts of the Bukhara region into two groups, taking into account the degree of coincidence of the share of land and labor resources, their employment in sectors of the economy, job security and the dynamics of the number of officially registered unemployed.

The first group with a high rate of growth in the number of unemployed included areas with low labor resources and areas with lower levels of employment and unemployment compared to the Bukhara region.

Studies conducted in the study of population formation show that in 2023, 31,2% of the population of the region was formed from the districts of the I-group and 68,8% - from the districts of the II-group.

It should be said that the main place in the formation of the urban population was occupied by the districts of the II group, and the main place in the formation of the rural population was occupied by the districts of the I group.

Zhondorsky, Olotsky, Peshko and Karakolsky districts are the areas with the least provision of labor resources in the I group of districts, and the cities of Bukhara and Kogon, Vobkent, Karovulbazar, Romitan, Shafirkon, Gijduvan, Bukhara and Kogonsky districts, which have especially rich labor resources, are in the II group.

Districts of group I, poorly provided with labor resources, occupy 66,8% of the area of the region, and compared with the Bukhara region, the population density is low, that is, 15,5 people per 1 sq. km. km.

2-table

At the beginning of 2021-2023, the population of Bukhara region will be formed at the expense of district groups, %

Indicators	Total Population		Urban Population		Rural Population		Population Growth 2021-2023		
	2021y	2023y.	2021y	2023y.	2021y	2023y	total	city	village
Years									

Districts of group I	27,2	27,6	18,2	18,5	31,4	31,4	31,2	26,2	31,6
II group of districts	72,8	72,4	81,8	81,5	68,6	68,6	68,8	73,8	68,4
Bukhara region - total	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100

Districts of the II group with surplus labor resources occupy 33,2% of the area of the region, and compared to the Bukhara region, per 1 sq. km account for 81,9 people, that is, the population density is higher.

By 2023, the total labor base of the region will be 1070,4 thousand people, which is 54,9% of the total population. In 2023, the number of labor resources decreased by 7,4 thousand people or 0,7% compared to 2021. At the same time, there was also a rate of decline in the number of labor resources compared to 2021.

In the analyzed years, in all districts of the Bukhara region, in some cases, a decrease in the average annual growth rate of labor resources was observed.

That is, two-thirds of the composition of the labor force increased due to the rural population. Therefore, special attention should be paid to rural areas in solving the problems of providing employment for the population of the region.

We have set ourselves the goal of studying the age structure of the labor resources of the region in order to ensure employment of the population and solve employment problems. One of the unique aspects characterizing the composition of the labor force of the region is that, according to the data of 2021, about 99,4% of the labor force of the region are the labor force of working age, 0,6% are people who have not reached working age and have left it. According to the data for 2021, 5,400 people in the labor force of the region are people who have not reached working age and have left it.

As a result of the study of employment of the population of the Bukhara region, the following factors of growth in the unemployment rate were identified:

- reduction of jobs in connection with the transition of management to market principles;
 - introduction of new technologies at regional enterprises;
 - creation of joint ventures equipped with modern equipment and requiring deep knowledge and skills from employees;
 - a product produced between enterprises of the state and non-state sectors
- change in the balance of volumes (works, services), a relative decrease in the volumes of products (works, services) produced at state-owned enterprises.

Thus, the growth of unemployment in the region is due to economic and socio-demographic factors, and the solution to the problem of employment is achieved through:

- stimulating the development of a wide range of activities, primarily the processing of agricultural raw materials, the production of consumer goods, building materials from local raw materials, as well as the creation of conditions for the expansion of individual entrepreneurship;

- the rapid development of the service sector, especially in areas of group II, a significant expansion of the types of social and construction services provided to the population. The service sector represents an untapped potential that can provide jobs not only for the unemployed, but also for an additional growing part of the labor force;

- the category of the population that cannot be provided with temporary work must be reliably protected by social protection, have guaranteed resources to meet their essential needs.

The results of the research show that freelancing is another way to ensure the employment of labor resources in the conditions of the current innovative economy.

7 Advantages of Being a Freelancer in 2023⁹¹

⁹¹<https://www.upwork.com/resources/advantages-of-being-a-freelancer#:~:text=Freelancing%20allows%20workers%20to%20build,in%20more%20clients%20than%20others.>

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